

I SHO‘BA. IQLIM O‘ZGARISHI: QOR QOPLAMI, TOG‘ MUZLIKLARI
DEGRADATSIYASI, XAVFLI GIDROMETEOROLOGIK HODISALAR

II СЕКЦИЯ. ИЗМЕНЕНИЕ КЛИМАТА: СНЕЖНЫЙ ПОКРОВ, ДЕГРАДАЦИЯ ГОРНЫХ
ЛЕДНИКОВ, ОПАСНЫЕ ГИДРОМЕТЕОРОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ЯВЛЕНИЯ

SECTION II. CLIMATE CHANGE: SNOW COVER, DEGRADATION OF MOUNTAIN
GLACIERS, DANGEROUS HYDROMETEOROLOGICAL PHENOMENA

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STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF DAILY RUNOFF CHANGES
IN THE PSKEM RIVER

Abstract. Mountain rivers of Central Asia are highly sensitive to climate change due to their dependence on snow and glacier melt processes. This study investigates long-term changes in daily runoff of the Pskem River during 1966–2020 using hydrological observations from the Mulala gauging station. The study compares the baseline climatic period (1966–1990) with the recent climatic period (1991–2020). Statistical approaches including mean daily discharge analysis, relative differences, coefficient of variation, and Mann–Kendall trend analysis were applied. The results demonstrate significant seasonal shifts in runoff formation under climate warming conditions. Earlier snowmelt contribution and increased spring discharge were observed, while reduced runoff was detected during the summer months. Trend analysis revealed statistically significant positive trends during spring and negative trends during summer.

Keywords: Pskem River, climate change, daily runoff, mountain hydrology, Mann-Kendall test, glacier melt, snowmelt runoff, Central Asia, hydrological trends, water resources

Over recent decades, climate change has become one of the dominant factors affecting mountain hydrological systems throughout the region. Rising air temperatures, changes in precipitation patterns, and accelerated glacier retreat have already altered seasonal runoff regimes in many river basins of Central Asia [1]. Previous studies have shown that increasing temperatures lead to earlier snowmelt onset, shifts in river flow timing, and changes in seasonal water availability [2]. Such transformations are especially important for arid and semi-arid regions where agriculture, hydropower, and water supply systems strongly depend on stable mountain runoff.

The study was based on long-term hydrological observations from the Mulala gauging station located on the Pskem River. Daily discharge data covering the period 1966–2020 were obtained from Uzhydromet archives. To assess climate-related changes in runoff formation, the entire observation period was divided into two sub-periods: the baseline climatic period (1966–1990) and the recent climatic period (1991–2020). Such division makes it possible to compare historical hydrological conditions with more recent conditions characterized by intensified regional warming.

Several statistical methods were applied to analyze changes in daily runoff characteristics. Mean daily discharge values were calculated for each day of the year for both climatic periods. Absolute and relative differences between the periods were then estimated to identify seasonal changes in runoff formation. In addition, variability of river discharge was evaluated using the coefficient of variation, which characterizes the degree of fluctuation in daily runoff values throughout the hydrological year. To identify long-term trends in daily runoff, the Mann–Kendall non-parametric trend test was applied together with Sen’s slope estimator. The Mann–Kendall test is widely used in hydrological research because it effectively detects monotonic trends without requiring normally distributed data. Sen’s slope estimator was additionally used to quantify the magnitude and direction of identified trends [3]. Statistical significance of the detected trends was evaluated at the 95% confidence level.

The analysis of mean daily discharge revealed distinct seasonal differences between the baseline and recent climatic periods (Fig. 1). Both periods demonstrate a typical mountain river regime characterized by low winter discharge and high spring-summer runoff associated with snow and glacier melt processes. Maximum river discharge occurs mainly during May and June, corresponding to intensive snowmelt in the mountainous part of the basin. However, the recent climatic period shows an earlier increase in river discharge compared to the historical baseline period. The hydrograph indicates that spring runoff formation currently begins several weeks earlier than during 1966–1990, reflecting accelerated snowmelt processes under rising air temperature conditions.

Fig. 1. Seasonal changes in mean daily discharge, discharge differences, and variability characteristics of the Pskem River during the baseline (1966–1990) and recent climatic periods (1991–2020).

Fig. 2. Mann–Kendall trend analysis of daily discharge changes in the Pskem River during 1965–2020.

Comparison of the two climatic periods also revealed a noticeable redistribution of runoff throughout the hydrological year (Fig. 1). During spring months, river discharge in the recent period became higher than during the baseline period, with the maximum positive difference reaching approximately +15 m³/s around the 150th day of the year. At the same time, discharge during summer months became lower than during the historical period, with the strongest negative anomalies

observed during July and August. The minimum differences reached approximately $-35 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ during the middle of the warm season. These results indicate that climate warming increases early snowmelt contribution while reducing water availability during late summer due to depletion of seasonal snow reserves and reduced glacier melt contribution.

The coefficient of variation analysis demonstrated substantial changes in runoff variability between the two climatic periods (Fig. 1). Higher variability was mainly observed during transitional hydrological seasons, particularly in spring and autumn. In the recent climatic period, coefficient of variation values exceeded 40–50% during several periods of the year, indicating increasingly unstable runoff conditions. The largest differences in variability were observed around days 50 and 250 of the hydrological year, suggesting stronger fluctuations in river discharge under changing climatic conditions. These results indicate that climate change affects not only mean river discharge but also the stability and predictability of seasonal runoff regimes.

Trend analysis using the Mann–Kendall test revealed statistically significant seasonal trends in daily runoff during 1965–2020 (Fig. 2). Positive trends were mainly detected during April and May, where increasing discharge corresponds to intensified and earlier snowmelt processes. In contrast, statistically significant negative trends dominated during July and August, indicating decreasing summer runoff. Sen’s slope values showed the strongest positive trends during spring and the strongest negative trends during the middle of summer. The concentration of statistically significant trends during the warm season confirms substantial seasonal redistribution of runoff under ongoing climate warming conditions [4].

Overall, the obtained results demonstrate considerable transformation of the hydrological regime of the Pskem River during recent decades. Earlier runoff formation and declining summer discharge may create increasing pressure on downstream water management systems, particularly for irrigation and hydropower sectors that depend on stable summer water availability. The identified seasonal runoff redistribution and increasing variability are consistent with hydrological changes observed in other glacier- and snow-fed river basins of Central Asia under climate warming conditions [5].

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ASSESSMENT OF CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACTS ON INFLOW TO THE KARAJ DAM (CASE STUDY: IRAN, KARAJ DAM)

Abstract. In this study, the role of climate change and its impacts on temperature and precipitation in the future period on the inflow to the Karaj Dam was evaluated using the LSTM and LSTM-FHO simulation methods. Inflow data, along with hydrometric and meteorological variables, were analyzed during the training and validation periods, and the best combination of predictor